

APPENDIX 1

NORMAL DISTRIBUTION OF REQUIREMENTS AFTER PREPROCESSING

	Min	Max	Centroids	σ_x
R1	1	5	4.167	1.208
R2	1	5	3.667	1.391
R3	1	5	4.5	0.994
R4	1	5	3.786	1.138
R5	1	5	4.405	1.149
R6	1	5	3.571	1.252
R7	2	5	4.429	0.77
R8	2	5	4.5	0.834
R9	1	5	4.071	1.156
R10	1	5	3.69	1.316
R11	1	5	4	1.23
R12	1	5	3.738	1.17
R13	1	5	3.452	1.4
R14	1	5	3.405	1.326
R15	1	5	3.095	1.376
R16	1	5	4.024	1.137
R17	3	5	4.405	0.798
R18	2	5	4.024	0.95
R19	1	5	3.905	1.165
R20	2	5	4.119	1.017
R21	2	5	4.238	1.031
R22	2	5	4.5	0.773
R23	1	5	4.143	1.117
R24	2	5	4.333	0.816
R25	1	5	4.167	0.853